

Activity Measurements in Aqueous Mixed Electrolyte Solutions. Part-6. Application of Scatchard and Pitzer Theories to the Results of E.M.F. Measurements in Ternary Mixtures of Hydrochloric Acid, Mono- or Di- or Trimethylammonium Chloride and Water of Constant Total Molality at Four different Temperatures

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The Scatchard and Pitzer treatments of mixed electrolyte solutions have been applied to the published results of e.m.f. measurements in cells without liquid junction of the type,

containing aqueous mixtures of HCl with mono- or di- or trimethylammonium chloride in different proportions but at constant total molality m ($= m_A + m_B$) ($m = 3, 2, 1, 0.75, 0.5, 0.25$ and 0.1), at four different temperatures ($5, 15, 25$ and 35°). The measured activity coefficients of HCl were in every case found to obey the Harned rule. The activity coefficients of all the three substituted ammonium chlorides in the different mixtures at all the four different temperatures have been calculated by the Scatchard and Pitzer methods. The results have been compared with the earlier published results of calculation by the Lim method.

In continuation of our earlier studies¹⁻³ on activity measurements in aqueous mixed electrolyte solutions, we have recently reported⁴ the results of e.m.f. measurements in cells of the type,

where MCl is either (i) $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2\cdot\text{HCl}$, or (ii) $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NH}\cdot\text{HCl}$, or (iii) $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N}\cdot\text{HCl}$. Measurements were made with the HCl and the methylammonium chloride components in different proportions but at constant total molalities m ($= 3, 2, 1, 0.75, 0.5, 0.25$ and 0.1), at four different temperatures over the temperature range $5-35^\circ$. Interpretation of the results was made in terms of the multicomponent ionic equilibrium theory of Lim ('all mixing coefficients')⁵.

There are however available two other semiempirical treatments of mixed electrolyte solutions

namely those of Scatchard⁶ and Pitzer⁷. It is of interest to see how far the calculations according to these two different treatments agree with the experimental results in comparison to the performance of the Lim treatment mentioned. It is the purpose of the present paper to discuss this point in detail. At constant total molality m ($= m_A + m_B$) of a binary mixture of two electrolytes A and B, the variation of the activity coefficient of the component A, for example, with composition can, in general, be expressed by an equation of the type,

$$\log \gamma_A = \log \gamma_A^0 + Q_A \gamma_B + R_A \gamma_B^2 \quad (1)$$

where γ_A and γ_A^0 are respectively the activity coefficients of the component A in the mixture, and in pure solution, at the same total molality m , γ_B is the molality fraction m_B/m of the second component,

and Q_A and R_A are constants at a given total molality independent of the mixture composition. A similar equation holds for the component B. Frequently, the linear form obtained by considering $R_A = 0$ in equation (1) has been found to express with sufficiently accuracy the measured activity coefficients of A; the electrolyte is then said to obey Harned's rule⁸.

The simplified Scatchard expression ('neutral electrolytes as components')⁶ for the activity coefficient of the component A in the mixture of two 1:1 electrolytes is

$$\log \gamma_A = \log \gamma_A^0 + [2(\phi_B^0 - \phi_A^0) + b_{AB}^{(0,1)} m + b_{AB}^{(0,2)} m^2 + b_{AB}^{(0,3)} m^3] \gamma_B / 4.6052 \quad (2)$$

Assuming Harned's rule to be obeyed by this component, equation (2) together with the appropriate form of equation (1) leads to

$$2(\phi_A^0 - \phi_B^0) + 4.6052 Q_A = b_{AB}^{(0,1)} m + b_{AB}^{(0,2)} m^2 + b_{AB}^{(0,3)} m^3 \quad (3)$$

so that the interaction coefficients b_{AB} can be calculated from the experimental γ_A values. Using these the activity coefficient of the other component in the mixture can then be calculated by means of an equation analogous to equation (2), namely,

$$\log \gamma_B = \log \gamma_B^0 + [2(\phi_A^0 - \phi_B^0) + b_{AB}^{(0,1)} m + b_{AB}^{(0,2)} m^2 + b_{AB}^{(0,3)} m^3] \gamma_A / 4.6052 \quad (4)$$

where ϕ_A^0 and ϕ_B^0 are the osmotic coefficients and γ_A^0 and γ_B^0 the activity coefficients of pure A and B components respectively, all at the total molality of the mixture.

The Pitzer equation⁷ for the activity coefficient of either component in a mixture of two 1:1 electrolytes with a common anion: HX(A) and MX(B), at a total molality (m) gives, for example, for the salt component,

$$\ln \gamma_{MX} = \ln \gamma_{MX}^0 + m_B [(\beta_{HX}^{(0)} - \beta_{MX}^{(0)}) + (\beta_{HX}^{(1)} - \beta_{MX}^{(1)}) \exp(-2m^{1/2}) + \theta_{HM} + m(C_{HX}^\phi - C_{MX}^\phi) + 1/2(m + m_A)\Psi_{HMX}] \quad (5)$$

where the quantities θ_{HM} and Ψ_{HMX} are respectively

the measures of binary and ternary interactions between the ions indicated by the subscripts. Further, the β and C terms for either electrolyte ($\beta^{(0)}$ and $\beta^{(1)}$, corresponding to the second virial coefficient, and C^ϕ , corresponding to the third) are strictly pure electrolyte parameters, and can be determined by least-squares fit of an equation of the type,

$$\ln \gamma^0 + A_\phi \left[\frac{m^{1/2}}{1 + 1.2m^{1/2}} + \frac{5}{3} \ln(1 + 1.2m^{1/2}) \right] = 2\beta^{(0)} m + \frac{1}{2}\beta^{(1)} [1 - \exp(-2m^{1/2}) (1 + 2m^{1/2} - 2m)] + \frac{3}{2}C^\phi m^2 \quad (6)$$

where A_ϕ is the Debye-Hückel limiting slope of the plot of ϕ vs \sqrt{m} . The Pitzer equation for ϕ^0 , corresponding to equation (6) for γ^0 , is

$$\phi^0 - 1 + A_\phi \frac{m^{1/2}}{1 + 1.2m^{1/2}} = \beta^{(0)} m + \beta^{(1)} \exp(-2m^{1/2}) m + C^\phi m^2 \quad (7)$$

which is useful for calculating ϕ_B^0 at different molalities, for use, e.g. in equations (2) and (3).

Lim's treatment of mixed electrolyte solutions ('all mixing coefficients')⁵ and its application to the experimental results of the present investigation have already been discussed in detail elsewhere⁴.

Method of calculation :

The values of the activity coefficient of aqueous solutions of mono-, di-, and trimethylammonium chlorides over the concentration range 0.0025–1.0 m have been determined by Jones, Spuhler and Felsing⁹ at 0°. The values over the molality range 0.2–1 m (which minimises the standard deviation of fit) were utilised by us⁴ for calculating (equation 6) the Pitzer coefficients ($\beta^{(0)}$, $\beta^{(1)}$ and C^ϕ) at 0°. Then by use of the values of the respective temperature derivatives as tabulated by Silvester and Pitzer¹⁰ (molality range upto 0.5) the parameter values at the other required temperatures (5, 15, 25 and 35°) were obtained (Table 1). Using these the activity and osmotic coefficient values (equations 6 and 7 respectively) of the three substituted ammonium chlorides at any molality upto 1.0 m

TABLE 1—PITZER PURE ELECTROLYTE PARAMETERS FOR HCl, CH₃NH₂ HCl, (CH₃)₂NH HCl and (CH₃)₃N HCl

Electrolyte	Parameter	273 15 K	278 15 K	288 15 K	298 15 K	308 15 K
HCl	$\beta^{(0)}$		0 181 8	0 178 7	0 175 6 (0 177 5) ^a	0 172 5
	$\beta^{(1)}$		0 299 1	0 292 5	0 293 9 (0 294 5) ^a	0 295 4
	C^ϕ		0 000 3	0 000 9	0 001 6 (0 000 8) ^a	0 002 2
CH ₃ NH ₂ HCl	$\beta^{(0)}$	0 231 3	0 231 9	0 233 0	0 234 1	0 235 3
	$\beta^{(1)}$	-0 474 2	-0 468 8	-0 458 0	-0 447 2	-0 436 4
	C^ϕ	-0 104 5	-0 104 5	-0 104 5	-0 104 5	-0 104 5
(CH ₃) ₂ NH HCl	$\beta^{(0)}$	0 297 3	0 297 4	0 297 6	0 297 8	0 298 1
	$\beta^{(1)}$	-0 776 5	-0 767 4	-0 749 2	-0 731 0	-0 712 8
	C^ϕ	-0 138 9	-0 138 9	-0 138 9	-0 138 9	-0 138 9
(CH ₃) ₃ N HCl	$\beta^{(0)}$	0 489 0	0 489 1	0 489 3	0 489 6	0 489 8
	$\beta^{(1)}$	-1 511 3	-1 493 6	-1 458 3	-1 423 0	-1 387 7
	C^ϕ	-0 256 4	-0 256 4	-0 256 4	-0 256 4	-0 256 4

^aLiterature values of HCl at 25° (ref 11)

at the four different temperatures mentioned were obtained⁴ (the calculation over the slightly extended concentration range is justified⁴).

For the other component, viz. HCl, a similar procedure was followed for calculating ϕ^0 at 5, 15 and 35°, involving the use of (i) the literature values¹² of activity coefficients at 25°, (ii) the temperature derivatives of the corresponding Pitzer coefficients, and (iii) equations (6) and (7). (The ϕ^0 value at 25° is directly available from literature¹²). Also, the γ^0 values at all the molalities considered (except 0.25 and 0.75 *m*) at the three other temperatures mentioned are also directly available from literature⁸. (The γ^0 values at the remaining two concentrations mentioned, at all four different temperatures, were obtained by the method of Downes¹³). The direct calculation (rather than through the use of the temperature derivatives of the Pitzer coefficients) of the ϕ^0 values from γ^0 values at all different molalities and temperatures, though possible in the case of the HCl component where such γ^0 values are available, would not have been possible in the case of the amine chloride components; hence the use of the same (indirect) procedure has been retained for the HCl component also for the sake of uniformity.

The Scatchard method : In the Scatchard method we have used the osmotic coefficient values (ϕ_B^0) of mono-, di-, and trimethylammonium chlorides at 5, 15, 25 and 35° to calculate (least-squares analysis of equation 3) the b_{AB} parameters of the binary mixtures in the molality range 0.5–1.0 *m*, using the values of (i) the osmotic coefficient of pure hydrochloric acid of corresponding molalities (ϕ_A^0) and (ii) the Harned coefficients (Q_A) of the HCl-MCl mixtures at the corresponding different total molalities, both at the said four different temperatures. Then by using these b_{AB} values for a particular mixture and the activity coefficient value of either the pure salt (γ_{MCl}^0) or the pure acid (γ_{HCl}^0) at the different molalities, both at four different temperatures, we calculate (equation 4 or 2 respectively) the activity coefficient values of the salt and the acid in the mixture.

The Pitzer method : In the Pitzer method, the $\beta^{(0)}$, $\beta^{(1)}$ and C^ϕ values of the mono-, di-, and trimethylammonium chlorides as also of HCl, and the γ^0 values of the pure acid solutions at different molalities have been used to obtain (analogue of equation 5) first the binary (θ) and ternary (ψ) interaction terms by means of a graphical method,

and finally, the activity coefficient values of the salt in the mixtures of different molalities at the four different temperatures. The graphical method consists in defining a quantity $\Delta \ln \gamma_{\text{HCl}}$ as the difference between the experimental values of $\ln \gamma_{\text{HCl}}$ in the mixtures (Table 2, Ref. 4) and those calculated from the analogue of equation (5) for the HCl component with θ and ψ set equal to zero. This yields

$$\Delta \ln \gamma_{\text{HCl}}/m_{\text{B}} = \theta_{\text{HM}} + \frac{1}{2} (m + m_{\text{A}}) \psi_{\text{HMCl}} \quad (8)$$

so that a plot of $(\Delta \ln \gamma_{\text{HCl}})/m_{\text{B}}$ vs $1/2 (m + m_{\text{A}})$ gives a straight line with intercept θ_{HM} and slope ψ_{HMCl} . Using such θ and ψ values, the activity coefficients of the different substituted ammonium chlorides in the mixtures of different molalities at the four temperatures can be calculated by equation (5).

TABLE 2—SCATCHARD'S MIXED ELECTROLYTE PARAMETERS OF MIXTURES OF HCl WITH DIFFERENT SUBSTITUTED METHYL AMMONIUM CHLORIDES

System	Parameter	278 15 K	288 15 K	298 15 K	308 15 K
HCl CH ₃ NH ₂	$b_{\text{AB}}^{(0,1)}$	0 059 6	0 096 1	0 099 8	0 101 7
HCl	$b_{\text{AB}}^{(0,2)}$	-0 391 5	-0 463 1	-0 456 8	-0 442 0
	$b_{\text{AB}}^{(0,3)}$	0 223 8	0 262 7	0 256 1	0 244 6
HCl (CH ₃) ₂ NH	$b_{\text{AB}}^{(0,1)}$	0 052 1	0 039 1	0 132 3	0 140 3
HCl	$b_{\text{AB}}^{(0,2)}$	-0 510 5	-0 417 4	-0 611 4	-0 587 4
	$b_{\text{AB}}^{(0,3)}$	0 296 9	0 232 6	0 342 3	0 328 4
HCl (CH ₃) ₃ N	$b_{\text{AB}}^{(0,1)}$	0 245 2	0 248 3	0 274 5	0 281 2
HCl	$b_{\text{AB}}^{(0,2)}$	-1 025 8	-0 991 4	-1 060 1	-1 044 3
	$b_{\text{AB}}^{(0,3)}$	0 568 1	0 546 8	0 609 0	0 605 2

Results and Discussion

The details of experimental procedure and the experimental (i) emf and (ii) γ_{HCl} values (equation 1 with $R_{\text{A}} = 0$) for all the three methylammonium chloride : HCl mixtures at all four different temperatures have been reported elsewhere⁴.

The method of calculation of the Scatchard mixed electrolyte parameters has been described earlier; the values are shown in Table 2. The reason for not considering the total molality sets for which

$m < 0.5$, is the same as discussed elsewhere^{1,3} in connection with results for other binary mixtures studied. The calculation of γ_{MCl} and γ_{HCl} for each mixture has also been described. The deviations $\Delta^{(S)} = [\log_{10} (\text{experimental activity coefficient}) - \log_{10} (\text{value calculated by least-squares fit to equation (2), for the HCl component}]$ have been calculated and found to be small; the standard deviations at each constant total molality $\sigma^{(S)}$ are shown in Table 3. The calculated values of the activity coefficient of the three amine chlorides in the said mixtures $\log \gamma_{\text{B}}^{(S)}$ are listed in Table 4

The graphical method mentioned earlier for the determination of the interaction terms θ and ψ is illustrated in Fig. 1 for the three substituted ammonium chloride : HCl mixtures at one temperature only (25°). The values obtained at all the four temperatures, together with their standard deviations are shown in Table 5. The activity coefficient values at the different temperatures have then been calculated by means of equation (5) using the Pitzer coefficient values of both the components and the pure methylammonium chloride solution activity coefficient values at the corresponding total molality. For the acid component, the deviations $\Delta^{(P)} [= \log_{10} (\text{experimental activity coefficient}) - \log_{10} (\text{value calculated by least-squares fit to the equation analogous to equation (5) for the HCl component}]$ have been calculated and found to be small; the standard deviations at each constant total molality $\sigma^{(P)}$ are shown in Table 3. The calculated values (equation 5) of the activity coefficients of the three substituted ammonium chlorides in the said mixtures $\log \gamma_{\text{B}}^{(P)}$ are listed in Table 4.

We now discuss the results obtained

(i) As mentioned earlier, the Lim treatment⁵ in addition to those of Scatchard⁶ and Pitzer⁷, is also available for calculating the γ values of the two components in a mixture. We have actually employed all three methods, though the results given here are only for the Scatchard and Pitzer treatments. It is interesting to compare the results obtained by the three different methods. It has been found

TABLE 3—STANDARD DEVIATIONS OF F11 OF THE LOG γ_{HCl} VALUES CALCULATED BY THE SCATCHARD, LIM AND PITZER METHODS WITH RESPECT TO THE EXPERIMENTAL VALUES AT THE FOUR DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Binary mixture	<i>m</i>	278.15 K				288.15 K				298.15 K				308.15 K			
		$\sigma \times 10^4$				$\sigma \times 10^4$				$\sigma \times 10^4$				$\sigma \times 10^4$			
		S	L	L*	P												
HCl · CH ₃ NH ₂ HCl	0.10	8	8	8	27	7	4	4	25	5	8	6	20	6	5	5	22
	0.25	10	0	0	46	10	3	2	43	9	1	1	39	9	4	3	35
	0.50	4	3	3	28	3	6	4	16	5	15	8	18	4	5	4	13
	0.75	1	2	1	4	3	2	1	4	3	5	3	11	1	1	1	11
	1.00	7	17	15	17	6	15	13	15	6	14	13	16	5	7	7	8
HCl · (CH ₃) ₂ NH HCl	0.10	15	8	5	49	17	8	7	49	11	87	47	47	13	3	2	45
	0.25	10	3	2	55	16	2	2	61	7	4	1	54	9	7	2	59
	0.50	3	7	7	18	5	12	10	18	5	6	5	17	3	9	7	23
	0.75	1	2	2	8	2	5	4	6	3	7	6	12	2	5	5	9
	1.00	10	16	16	20	7	15	14	17	12	16	12	23	8	10	9	13
HCl · (CH ₃) ₃ N HCl	0.10	26	2	0	84	25	4	1	83	22	3	1	78	16	5	1	64
	0.25	19	3	2	93	18	5	5	90	20	5	5	93	15	7	5	81
	0.50	5	11	6	46	10	11	11	66	3	8	7	47	5	9	7	50
	0.75	5	23	8	10	7	49	13	19	7	14	8	16	5	20	7	10
	1.00	7	41	10	10	7	31	8	10	12	34	9	13	10	38	18	19

S stands for Scatchard, L for Lim, L for (Lim's) alternative method of calculation and P for Pitzer.

TABLE 4—ACTIVITY COEFFICIENTS OF METHYLAMMONIUM CHLORIDES IN MIXTURES WITH HCl, CALCULATION BY USING THE SCATCHARD AND PITZER EQUATIONS

<i>m</i>	<i>y_A</i>	278.15 K		288.15 K		298.15 K		308.15 K	
		$-\log \gamma_B^{(S)}$	$-\log \gamma_B^{(P)}$						
CH ₃ NH ₂ ·HCl									
1.0	1.000 2	0.201	0.292	0.203	0.283	0.207	0.282	0.210	0.280
	0.901 1	0.206	0.288	0.208	0.280	0.211	0.279	0.215	0.278
	0.700 6	0.215	0.279	0.217	0.273	0.220	0.274	0.223	0.274
	0.500 0	0.224	0.270	0.225	0.266	0.228	0.268	0.231	0.269
	0.300 0	0.233	0.260	0.234	0.259	0.237	0.261	0.239	0.262
	0.099 9	0.242	0.251	0.243	0.251	0.245	0.253	0.248	0.256
0.75	0.897 5	0.200	0.246	0.203	0.242	0.206	0.243	0.209	0.243
	0.498 6	0.214	0.240	0.216	0.239	0.219	0.240	0.222	0.242
	0.099 8	0.229	0.234	0.230	0.235	0.232	0.237	0.235	0.239
0.50	0.900 2	0.186	0.209	0.187	0.207	0.191	0.209	0.193	0.210
	0.699 1	0.193	0.211	0.194	0.210	0.197	0.211	0.199	0.213
	0.500 0	0.199	0.212	0.200	0.212	0.203	0.213	0.205	0.215
	0.099 9	0.212	0.214	0.213	0.215	0.215	0.217	0.217	0.219
0.25	0.897 0	0.156	0.165	0.158	0.166	0.160	0.167	0.162	0.169
	0.496 0	0.167	0.172	0.169	0.173	0.170	0.174	0.172	0.176
	0.099 6	0.177	0.178	0.179	0.180	0.180	0.181	0.183	0.183
0.1	1.000 3	0.114	0.118	0.116	0.119	0.118	0.121	0.119	0.123
	0.898 9	0.116	0.120	0.117	0.120	0.119	0.122	0.121	0.124
	0.699 9	0.119	0.122	0.121	0.123	0.123	0.125	0.124	0.126
	0.499 2	0.123	0.125	0.124	0.125	0.126	0.127	0.127	0.129
	0.298 7	0.126	0.127	0.127	0.128	0.129	0.130	0.131	0.132

Table -4 (Contd.)

(CH ₃) ₂ NH ₂ .HCl										
1.0	0.900 2	0.234	0.341	0.234	0.336	0.235	0.340	0.235	0.341	
	0.699 4	0.241	0.324	0.241	0.322	0.243	0.325	0.244	0.326	
	0.500 0	0.249	0.308	0.249	0.307	0.251	0.309	0.251	0.310	
	0.299 4	0.256	0.292	0.257	0.292	0.259	0.294	0.260	0.295	
	0.100 0	0.264	0.276	0.265	0.276	0.266	0.278	0.268	0.279	
0.75	0.898 6	0.226	0.285	0.225	0.283	0.226	0.285	0.227	0.286	
	0.697 5	0.232	0.278	0.232	0.277	0.233	0.278	0.234	0.279	
	0.500 2	0.238	0.271	0.238	0.270	0.239	0.272	0.240	0.273	
	0.299 3	0.244	0.264	0.244	0.264	0.245	0.265	0.247	0.266	
	0.099 8	0.250	0.257	0.251	0.257	0.252	0.258	0.253	0.260	
0.50	0.900 1	0.206	0.235	0.206	0.234	0.207	0.237	0.208	0.238	
	0.699 6	0.212	0.235	0.213	0.234	0.213	0.237	0.215	0.238	
	0.499 9	0.219	0.235	0.219	0.235	0.220	0.237	0.221	0.238	
	0.299 9	0.225	0.235	0.225	0.235	0.227	0.237	0.228	0.238	
	0.100 0	0.231	0.234	0.232	0.235	0.233	0.237	0.235	0.238	
0.25	0.700 0	0.175	0.184	0.176	0.185	0.176	0.186	0.178	0.188	
	0.498 9	0.181	0.188	0.182	0.188	0.183	0.190	0.184	0.191	
	0.299 5	0.187	0.191	0.188	0.192	0.189	0.193	0.191	0.195	
	0.100 1	0.194	0.195	0.194	0.195	0.195	0.197	0.197	0.198	
	0.900 0	0.123	0.127	0.124	0.128	0.125	0.130	0.126	0.131	
0.10	0.700 6	0.127	0.130	0.128	0.131	0.129	0.133	0.130	0.134	
	0.500 4	0.131	0.133	0.132	0.134	0.133	0.136	0.134	0.137	
	0.100 0	0.139	0.139	0.140	0.141	0.141	0.142	0.142	0.143	
	(CH ₃) ₃ N.HCl									
	1.0	0.699 9	0.289	0.442	0.286	0.436	0.283	0.436	0.280	0.435
0.499 7		0.296	0.405	0.293	0.401	0.291	0.400	0.288	0.399	
0.300 0		0.303	0.369	0.301	0.365	0.298	0.364	0.296	0.363	
0.100 0		0.311	0.333	0.308	0.330	0.306	0.328	0.304	0.326	
0.700 2		0.272	0.359	0.270	0.355	0.269	0.355	0.268	0.355	
0.75	0.500 1	0.279	0.341	0.276	0.373	0.275	0.337	0.275	0.336	
	0.299 7	0.285	0.323	0.283	0.320	0.282	0.318	0.281	0.318	
	0.100 1	0.292	0.304	0.289	0.302	0.288	0.300	0.287	0.299	
	0.900 1	0.237	0.294	0.236	0.291	0.236	0.291	0.236	0.291	
	0.699 5	0.245	0.289	0.244	0.287	0.248	0.287	0.243	0.287	
0.50	0.499 6	0.253	0.285	0.252	0.283	0.251	0.282	0.251	0.282	
	0.299 8	0.262	0.281	0.260	0.279	0.259	0.278	0.259	0.277	
	0.100 0	0.270	0.276	0.268	0.275	0.267	0.273	0.266	0.272	
	0.899 1	0.188	0.212	0.189	0.211	0.189	0.212	0.190	0.213	
	0.700 4	0.197	0.216	0.198	0.215	0.198	0.216	0.199	0.217	
0.25	0.498 9	0.207	0.220	0.207	0.219	0.207	0.220	0.208	0.220	
	0.299 8	0.216	0.224	0.216	0.223	0.216	0.224	0.216	0.224	
	0.699 4	0.140	0.147	0.141	0.148	0.142	0.148	0.142	0.149	
	0.497 9	0.147	0.152	0.143	0.152	0.148	0.152	0.149	0.153	
	0.298 6	0.153	0.156	0.154	0.156	0.154	0.157	0.155	0.157	

that the std. devs. of fit, with the experimental values, of the log γ_{HCl} values calculated according to the different treatments at all four different temperatures, are (a) larger for the Pitzer method as compared to the other methods, (b) almost comparable in magnitude in the case of the Scatchard and

the Lim methods. Also, the Pitzer approach gives different activity coefficient values for the salts as compared to the other two methods.

(ii) The Pitzer binary interaction term (θ_{HM}) obtained for all three alkylammonium chloride mix-

TABLE 5—PITZER INTERACTION PARAMETERS θ AND ψ FOR THREE HCl SUBSTITUTED AMMONIUM CHLORIDE MIXTURES

System	$-\theta$	$-\psi$	σ	$-\theta$	$-\psi$	σ
	278 15 K			288 15 K		
HCl-CH ₃ NH ₂ -HCl	0.055 5	0.003 0	0.003 1	0.037 1	0.0277	0.003 9
HCl-(CH ₃) ₂ NH-HCl	0.076 4	0.003 0	0.004 9	0.063 6	0.017 1	0.003 9
HCl-(CH ₃) ₃ N-HCl	0.099 3	0.007 3	0.002 4	0.086 6	0.026 2	0.004 0
		298 15 K		308 15 K		
HCl-CH ₃ NH ₂ -HCl	0.028 0	0.035 6	0.008 3	0.019 0	0.049 7	0.003 6
HCl-(CH ₃) ₂ NH-HCl	0.058 2	0.006 1	0.005 8	0.049 8	0.007 6	0.004 6
HCl-(CH ₃) ₃ N-HCl	0.080 8	0.018 1	0.003 3	0.074 5	0.010 4	0.004 1

Fig 1 Plot of $1/m_B \Delta \ln \gamma_{HCl}$ vs $1/2 (m + m_A)$ for the three amine chloride-HCl mixtures at 298.15 K

tures studied at 25° (results shown in Table 5), follow the order $\theta_{H^+-CH_3NH_3^+} (-0.028) > \theta_{H^+-(CH_3)_2NH_2^+} (-0.058) > \theta_{H^+-(CH_3)_3NH^+} (-0.081)$. Our earlier reported¹ $\theta_{H^+-(CH_3)_4N^+}$ values (-0.167) at the same temperature, and the value reported¹ by Robinson *et al.*¹⁴ also at the same temperature, $\theta_{H^+-NH_4^+} = -0.0165$, are consistent with the above values. These values clearly show that as the size of the cation in the series increases, together with a gradual decrease of the net surface charge density, the binary interaction term becomes increasingly more negative.

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